

EFFECT OF MICROSTRUCTURE CONTROL ON THERMAL AND ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITIES OF CNF/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In order to obtain the high performance materials with high electrical and thermal conductivity, carbon nano fiber (CNF) dispersed aluminum matrix (CNF/Al) composites is suitable materials, because CNF has superior mechanical properties, high thermal and electrical properties. In order to obtain the high performance CNF/Al composites, the control of fiber direction is very important, because fiber has high anisotropy. In this study, vapor grown carbon fiber (VGCF) was used, which is one of CNF. The two preparations of the composites were attempted in order to control the fiber direction of CNF. One is the rolling after sintering, and another is the sintering after rolling. Then, the effect of the fiber direction, the rolling texture of Al matrix and the density of the composites on the thermal conductivity and the electrical conductivity was investigated. Fiber orientation in composites was enhanced by rolling rate. Furthermore, by enhancing the fiber direction, the rolling direction of the electrical conductivity of the composites was improved, and the vertical direction was decreased. On the other hand, the prediction of the thermal conductivity using theoretical consideration showed that the enhancement of fiber orientation affect to the improvement of thermal conductivity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, the miniaturization, the high-density integration and the high power of electronic devices have been developing because of the development of automobile and IT technology. Therefore, the efficient heat missing and the lower difference of thermal expansion between electric substrate and heat sink are required. In general, the properties of heat sink are required to have high thermal conductivity, same thermal expansion for semi-conductor and good mechanical properties between room temperature and 300°C. As many kinds of properties are required for heat-sink, it seems that the utilization of the metal matrix composites (MMC) is suitable. Actually, many composites have been developing such as SiC/ Al composites, C/ Al composites and C/ Cu composites for heat sink materials. Carbon material as dispersant has good advantage because of good thermal conductivity, electrical conductivity and low thermal expansion. There are many kinds of carbon materials, for example, graphite, diamond, carbon fiber, graphene and so on. These characters are completely different for each carbon materials. Vapor grown carbon fiber (VGCF) seems to be most suitable materials for dispersant of composites because of its superior mechanical properties and high cost performance. This fiber is one of carbon nanofiber (CNF), and has good mechanical properties and good thermal and electrical conductivity along fiber direction. Therefore, VGCF is expected as high performance heat sink materials by integrating with pure Al [1-3]. However, the control of fiber direction in Al matrix is required because of its high anisotropy for properties. Therefore, the enhancement of the orientation of CNF in composites is very important in order to obtain the high performance CNF/Al composites. J. M. Hilding et al [4] reported CNT was oriented in liquid with AC electric field and then fabricated the CNT oriented sheet. But this method is complex and its treatment is difficult. In this study, the rolling was attempted in order to enhance the orientation of fiber. Because, the rolling is very simple process for the manufacturing. Composites are expected to obtain high thermal conductivity and electrical conductivity for particular direction by rolling. Consequently,

we can obtain high performance heat sink with high thermal conductivity and high anisotropic properties. On the other hand, this composites is expected to use the power transmission line and wiring in electrical packaging.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Starting materials used in this study, which obtain the composites, are aluminum powders with $3\mu\text{m}$ in average diameter and VGCF with $0.15\text{-}0.2\mu\text{m}$ in diameter and $10\text{-}20\mu\text{m}$ in length (Showa Denko Co., Ltd). Volume fraction of VGCF in composites is 5-40 vol. %. As as-received VGCF aggregates and forms secondary particles, aggregated VGCF was loosened by dipping in mixed acid (mixture of nitric acid and sulfuric acid) with ultrasonic vibration. After adding Al powders to VGCF, mixed powders was stirred by ultrasonic vibration and then boll-milled in V type ball milling machine at room temperature. Composites were fabricated by two methods. One is heat-treated at 823K for 2hr. after cold rolling. Mixed powder was inserted in Cu tube with 11mm in diameter, and then the edge of tube was chipped. Chipped tube was cold-rolled with 10-40% in rolling rate. Another is as follows; mixed powders was inserted to graphite mold with 100mm in diameter, and then, sintered by spark plasma sintering under the condition of 100A in current density with pulse current, 150MPa in applied pressure and 10 min in keeping time, and then applied pressure and temperature was increased gradually, and finally VGCF/ Al composites were obtained under the condition of 823K, 15MPa and 15 min. The composites were rolled at room temperature. Rolling rate per one process is 2 % and the composites were heat-treated 723K for 60 min in order to relieve the working stress. By repeating this process, the rolled composites with 10% in rolling rate was obtained. Density of the composites was estimated by Archimedes method. Microstructure was observed by optical microscopy and scanning microscopy (SEM), and then estimated the fiber orientation from photograph of microstructure. Electrical conductivity was estimated by four point prove method. Thermal conductivity was predicted from microstructure and theoretical equation based on rule of mixture.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the densification behavior of two types composites prepared by different method. One is rolled composites after sintering. Another is the sintered composites after rolling of mixed powders. The relative density of the rolled composites after sintering was higher than that of the sintered composites after rolling of mixed powders. The relative density of the sintered composites without rolling and the sintered composites with 10% rolling were 94.9% and 97.6%, respectively. But the composites prepared by rolled composites after sintering was fractured by over 10% rolling. On the other hand, the effect of the rolling to mixed powders in room temperature on the densification is week. But the high temperature is effective for the improvement of the relative density. In addition, the relative density was improved by the rolling for each sample, which is caused by the vanishing of aggregated VGCF by share deformation by rolling.

Figure 1: Effect of the rolling on relative density of composites. Open circle shows the rolled composites after sintering. X - mark shows the sintered composites after rolling the mixed powder.

Elongation of Al grain along rolling direction by rolling was observed. In order to evaluate the elongation of Al grain, the aspect ratio of grain was measured from over 200 grains in optical microscopy image. Fig. 2 shows the distribution of aspect ratio of Al grain in composites. The aspect ratio of mixed Al powder without sintering and Al grains in composites without rolling was distributed during 1-2, and there very few grains with over 3 in aspect ratio. This shows that grain forms isotropic. On the other hand, 1-2 in aspect ratio decreased and over 3 increased in Al grains in composites rolled with 20% and 40% in rolling rate. This result shows Al grain in matrix in composites elongated and the composites have anisotropic structure.

Fig. 3 shows the microstructure of VGCF/Al composites after rolling with 40% in rolling rate. Composites were fabricated by sintering after rolling. VGCF was aggregated at the boundary of Al grain. Al grains were elongated along rolling direction. After 40% rolling, pores were vanished, and VGCF in all composites still aggregated around the interface.

Figure 2: Effect of rolling rate on aspect ratio of Al grain in composites. (a) is as-mixed powder. (b), (c) and (d) are 0%, 20% and 40% in rolling rate, respectively.

Figure 3: SEM images of CNF/Al composites after rolling with 40% in rolling rate. Composites were fabricated by sintering after rolling. (b) is enlargement of (a).

Fig. 4 shows the angle between VGCF and rolling direction in rolled composites after sintering. (a) is without rolling, and (b) is with 40% rolling. This figure shows the influence of fiber orientation on rolling. Estimation of fiber orientation was measured by the angle between rolling direction and fiber direction. By rolling, the distribution of angle sifted to 0° side. It shows that fiber direction tend to move along rolling direction. Especially, the z-axis direction was suppressed by rolling, strongly.

Figure 4: Angle between VGCF and rolling direction, (a) without rolling and (b) rolled sample with 40% in rolling rate, respectively.

Fig. 5 shows that electrical conductivity of sintered composites after rolling by mixed powders. The electrical conductivity was estimated in rolling direction and in its perpendicular direction, respectively. The composites have lower electrical conductivity compared with monolithic Al block, which is caused by lower electrical conductivity of VGCF and lower density. Electrical conductivity of VGCF/Al composites along rolling direction was improved, but its vertical direction was decreased. This tendency was enhanced dramatically as increasing a rolling rate.

Table 1 shows the calculation results of thermal conductivity of the rolled composites after sintering. Calculation was performed by using the rule of mixture. The following equation is the rule of mixture of thermal conductivity for the composites with three-dimensional random orientation used in this study.

$$U_c = V_f \cdot U_{fl} \cdot \frac{3}{8} + (1 - V_f) \cdot U_m$$

Hence, U_c is the thermal conductivity of the composites, U_f is the thermal conductivity of VGCF, U_m is the thermal conductivity of matrix, and V_f is the volume fraction of fiber.

Following is the rule of mixture with random orientation in two dimensions [5].

$$U_{c_{x-y}} = \left(\frac{U_{fl}}{2} + \frac{U_{f\perp}}{2} \right) \cdot V_f + (1 - V_f) \cdot U_m$$

Hence, $U_{c_{x-y}}$ is the thermal conductivity of x-y plane in composites, U_{fl} is the thermal conductivity of fiber direction of VGCF, $U_{f\perp}$ is the thermal conductivity of vertical direction for fiber axis, U_m is the thermal conductivity of matrix, and V_f is the volume fraction of fiber.

Following is the case considering particulate pores in composites [5].

$$\lambda_{eff} = \frac{1}{4} \left[\lambda_p (3v_p - 1) + \lambda_s (3v_s - 1) + \left(\left[\lambda_p (3v_p - 1) + \lambda_s (3v_s - 1) \right]^2 + 8\lambda_p \lambda_s \right)^{1/2} \right]$$

Hence, λ_{eff} is the thermal conductivity of composites, λ_p is the thermal conductivity of cavity, λ_s the thermal conductivity of solid-phase, v_p is the volume fraction of cavity, and v_s is the volume fraction of solid phase. Results shows that the thermal conductivity could raise up to 15% of thermal conductivity by improving the fiber orientation of VGCF than that of the composites with random orientation of fiber. In addition, by considering relative density, thermal conductivity decreased about 8% for the composites with random orientation of fiber. But the thermal conductivity will improve by improving fiber orientation and densification by rolling.

Figure 5: Electrical conductivity for rolling direction and its vertical direction of pure Al block and 10vol. % CNF/Al composites prepared by spark sintering process and rolling process at room temperature.

Table.1: Calculation results of thermal conductivity.

Assumption of relative density as 100%

	Thermal conductivity for the difference of orientation of CNF[W/mK]		
	Random orientation	Two dimensional orientation(x-y)	One dimensional orientation
5vol%CNF/Al(Relative density100%)	248	255	285

Considering actual relative density

	Thermal conductivity with randum orientation of CNTCNF[W/mK]
5vol%CNF/Al without rolling (Relative density94.9%)	229
5vol%CNF/Al with 10 % rolling (Relative density97.6%)	239

4 CONCLUSION

After fabricating the composites by sintering of mixed VGCF and Al powders, the rolling process was performed in order to control the direction of VGCF in Al matrix. Then the effect of direction of VGCF, the rolling texture of Al matrix and the density of the composites on the thermal conductivity and the electrical conductivity was investigated. Following is our conclusions;

- 1) As increasing rolling rate, the relative density of the composites was improved. The improvement of the density of the composites by rolling after sintering was higher than that by sintering after rolling. 10% in rolling rate was limit in case of rolling after sintering.
- 2) Fiber orientation in composites was enhanced by rolling. Furthermore, by enhancing the fiber direction, the rolling direction of the electrical conductivity of the composites improved and the vertical direction decreased. On the other hand, the prediction of the thermal conductivity using theoretical consideration showed that the enhancement of fiber orientation affect to the improvement of thermal conductivity.

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